

Research Article

Teachers Involvement in School Decision Making and School Performance in Primary Schools of Elu Gelan Woreda

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Abstract

The leading purpose of this study was to investigate the teachers' involvement in school decision making and school performance in Elu Gelan woreda primary schools. Quantitative approach and Correlation design was employed. Six primary schools were drawn from 33 schools using simple random sampling technique. The total 186 (180 teachers, and 6 principals) respondents are included to the study. The data were collected through questionnaire, interview and document review. Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analyze quantitative data. Qualitative data was analyzed by summarizing and re-summarizing. The findings of the study show that teachers' involvement in planning and monitoring was found to be moderate. The result of one way of ANOVA at 95% showed absence of statically significance difference between six sampled schools. The extent of participation in different areas of school decision making is insufficient and there was statically significance difference in teachers' involvement among six schools. Generally, the performance of school was found to be not meeting standard. It was, thus, concluded that teachers role in school decision-making was not given due attentions in primary schools under the study. It was recommended that WOE need to assign trained and experienced principals and train principals who can empower teachers to involve and improve the decision making practices and performances of schools.

Key words: Decision making, Participation; School performance

Introduction

Schools are social centers that work with the community and are part of the community. The schools cannot exist separately from community. Schools need the assistance of community to accomplish their intended objective [1]. According to [2], using a group to make a decision has many potential advantages over decisions made by one individual or leader.

Local level educational performance can be measured using inspection framework or by analyzing dimensions like access, efficiency, management, educational finance etc. Much of the school performance literature draws upon educational production functions or school productivity traditions [3,4]. Underlying many of the models used in this type of research is the basic assumption that causal claims can be made about school performance.

The Ethiopian Education and Training Policy [5], gave a special attention and action priority to the change of educational organization and management of the country. Accordingly, the educational management of the school was set to a democratic leadership which participate both School Board and Parent-Teacher Students Association committee consisting of members from the community, teachers and students [6].

[7], also indicated that for enhancing the effectiveness and efficiency of schools as well as providing quality education to the community participatory decision making is essential. Moreover, for enhancing schools performance and students achievement participatory decision making at school level is vital.

However, according to the annual report of primary schools' of West Shoa Zone Elu Gelan woreda in [8], there are challenges faced teaches involvement decision making in schools. Some of these challenges were: teachers' motivation to their work and decisions made without their participation, low acceptance of decisions made by school principal, who leads to low school performance. Thus, the researcher was motivated to assess the primary school teachers' involvement in school decision making and school performance in primary schools of Elu Gelan woreda.

As regards the role played by teachers, [9], writes that "without the participation of teachers, changes in education are impossible".

So that this research was carried out to investigate whether there is a significant correlation between the teachers' involvement in school management and school performance in primary schools. Hence, the study was intended to explain how the teachers involve in decision making and in school management process and its relation with school performance in the study area.

To achieve the purpose of the study, the following basic questions would be dealt with:

1. To what extent do primary school principals practice involving teachers in school management?
2. To what extent do primary schools of Elu Gelan woreda perform?
3. What relation exists between decision-making practice and schools' performance in Elu Gelan Woreda primary schools?

Methodology Research Design

This section of the paper presents for readers the detail of research designs employed, population of the study, sampling techniques, key tools used for data collection, sources of data and best methods used for analysis. In this study correlation design was applied as the primary purpose of study is to study primary school principals' practice in involving teachers in decision making and relationship with school performance was investigated.

Population, Sample Size and Sampling Techniques

All primary school teachers and principals of Elu Gelan woreda primary schools were the target population. In Elu Gelan Woreda, there were 33 primary schools. Out of these schools, the researcher selected 6(six) or 18.18% by employing simple random sampling technique. Accordingly, Gora, Ejaji, Kiltu Ilala, Lalistu Gotara, Dirki Benaso and Kersa primary schools, were selected.

In this study, because of the total number of teachers and principals were 245, which were greater than 200, so it is difficult to participate all of them into the study because of their number was not manageable with time and other resources. So, through simple random and availability sampling techniques 186 teachers and principals included to the study.

The three major data collecting instruments were used. There were: 1) self-made questionnaire 2) document review and 3) interview guide.

Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used to analysis the data. Specifically, mean, standard deviation, ANOVA and correlation coefficient were used. In addition to that document review and interview data were integrated and narrated into quantitative data analysis by categorizing them into theme.

According to Best and Khan (1999) [8] in involving participants in the research work, it is important considering the ethical principles laid down to protect them. Moreover, all participants of the study were verbally informed about the purpose and benefit of the study just to secure their permission. Any data and information given by them kept confidential so that no one has the opportunity to relate the response to anyone of them and the data and information they provided would not be used for anything other than this study.

Results and Discussion

This part of the paper gives the detail understanding of the study based up on the data collected both through quantitatively and qualitatively from the study area. School principals were responsible for encouraging teachers and other school community participation in different areas of school decision-making. In a situation where decision is made independently by principals, teachers' and other school communities' commitment and initiation for effective implementation as well as proper utilization of resource in decision-making could be questionable. In this regard, [8] explains that management is decision-making. As regards the role played by teachers, [9], writes that "without the participation of teachers, changes in education are impossible".

Table 1: Teachers participation in planning and monitoring

Items			Gora	Lalistu Gotera	Dirki Benaso	Ejaji	Ilala	Kersa	Total		
									N	M	SD
1	Planning schools activities.	M	2.68	3.00	2.87	2.19	2.42	3.16	186	2.72	1.69
		SD	0.83	0.86	0.72	0.98	1.03	3.60			
		M	2.81	2.87	2.84	2.52	2.39	2.58	186	2.67	0.82
		SD	0.70	0.85	0.67	0.99	0.88	0.67			
2	Setting the mission, vision and values of the school	M	2.71	2.81	2.74	2.19	2.42	2.58	186	2.58	0.87
3	Determine the mechanism of supervising plan implementation	SD	0.84	0.75		0.75	1.12	0.76			
		M	2.733	2.893	0.82	2.300	1.976	2.773			
		SD	0.790	0.820	2.816	0.906	1.010				
		Average			0.736			1.676		2.65	1.12

As indicate on table1, teachers participation in planning school activities of study area show relatively high score (M=2.72, SD=1.69), followed by the setting mission vision values of schools (M=2.67, SD=0.82). Generally in the study areas teachers participation in planning and monitoring is moderate (M=2.65; SD=1.12).

Table 2: One way ANOVA results involvement in planning and supervision

involvement in planning and supervision	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	80.543	5	16.109	1.88	
Within Groups	1152.194	180	6.401		0.11
Total	1232.737	185			

Table 3: Participation in decision curriculum and supervision

The result showed the there is no statically significance difference (F (1, 185) =1.88, P= 0.11). It can be

Items	Responses	Responses							Total		
		Gora	Lalistu-Gotera	Dirqi Benaso	Ejaji	Ilala	Kersa	N	M	SD	
1.	Setting the learning objectives.	M	2.77	2.94	2.71	2.32	2.45	2.46	186	2.64	0.86
	SD	0.84	0.85	0.90	0.65	1.02	0.79				
2.	Deciding on the format of lesson plan.	M	2.87	2.81	2.77	2.52	2.58	2.66	186	2.66	0.94
	SD	0.92	0.79	0.95	0.95	1.15	0.84				
3.	Evaluating how well the department is operating.	SD	0.85	0.78	1.08	0.85	1.19	0.85	186	2.70	1.62
	M	2.77	2.97	2.81	2.45	2.65	2.55				
4.	Developing procedures for assessing student achievement.	M	3.03	2.74	2.58	2.87	2.35	2.71	186	2.71	0.95
	SD	0.85	1.003	0.67	0.81	0.99	0.84				
5.	Determining when instructional supervision can be delivered	M	2.862	2.860	2.678	2.620	2.496	2.606	186	2.72	1.06
	SD	0.882	0.870	0.950	0.844	1.253	0.812				
Total averages										2.68	1.06

understood that there is no statically significance difference schools in involving between teachers in planning and monitoring.

As can be seen from Table 3, teachers involvement level in curriculum and instruction issues was found to be modest (M = 2.68, SD = 1.06, N = 186). In the study area, teachers determine when instructional supervision will be made (M = 2.72, SD = 0.96).

Teachers in decision-making practice developing procedures for assessing student achievement (M= 2.71, SD= 0.95) and evaluating how well the department is working (M= 2.70; SD= 1.62) both at moderate level. The finding that says teachers determine when classroom supervision done; participate in determining assessment procedure and in overall curriculum and instructional issues at modest level shows that principals are in-

volved teachers on key school functions.

Results obtained from some documents such as staff minutes of meeting supported the finding. To investigate whether the six schools differ in involving teachers in curriculum and instruction issues, null hypothesis was stated and tested at 95% confidence interval. The null hypothesis stated was that there was no statistical significance difference between all the six schools in involving teachers. Alternative hypothesis claimed that at least one school may differ from the others. One way ANOVA with post Hoc was conducted at 95%confidence interval.

Table 4: one way ANOVA result curriculum and supervision

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	152.452	5	30.490	2.303	.087
Within Groups	2382.839	180	13.238		
Total	2535.290	185			

Participation in management of school finance

The result of one way ANOVA showed the absence statically deference management of participation (F(1, 185) = 2.30; p =0.09). It can be understood that with curriculum and supervision all school principals did not differ.

Table 5: Teachers involvement in management of school finance

No										Total		
			Gora	Lalistu Gotera	Dirqi Benaso	Ejaji	Ilala	Kersa		N	M	SD
1	Formulation of school budget	M	2.97	2.67	2.65	2.87	2.58	2.48				
		SD	0.98	0.91	1.17	0.08	1.11	186		186	2.69	
2	Determining means of income generation	M	3.0	2.97	2.48	2.97	2.39	0.81				
		SD	0.98	0.91	0.92	0.91	1.05	2.55	186	1.02		
3	Sharing of budget for the department	M	3.0	3.0	2.61	3.0	2.58	0.76				
		SD	.98	0.96	0.95	.98	0.92	2.52	186	186	2.68	0.09
4	Implementation of school budget.	M	3.1	2.71	2.61	2.94	2.45	0.92				
		SD	1.0	0.90	0.84	0.92	1.02	2.65	186	186	2.71	0.98
5	Follow up of school budget performance.	M	3.2	2.55	2.52	3.0	2.55	0.95				
		SD	0.97	0.88	0.99	0.89	0.88	2.48	186	186	2.75	0.96
								0.99				
	Total Average	M	3.05	2.78	2.57	2.96	2.51			186	2.73	
		SD	0.98	0.91	0.97	0.75	0.99	2.54			0.98	
								0.88			2.71	0.80

As can be seen from Table 5, involvement of teachers in school finance management was found to be at average (M = 2.71; SD = 0.80); level involvement implementation of school budget (M = 2.75; SD = 0.96) teachers involvement in budget formulation was low (M=2.68SD, 0.1) follow up of school budget performance (M=2.73; SD=0.98) and determining means of income generation was lowest (M = 2.69; SD = 1.02) were all at average level. From these findings, it can be understood that principals of the primary schools study area involve teachers in diversification and management of school finance, this will enable teachers to develop know how about budget preparation, utilization and efficiency.

One way ANOVA with post hoc was conducted at 95% confidence interval. Computing one – way ANOVA was appropriate as the schools are more than two (Gay, Mills,& Airason 2009). The null hypothesis stated claimed that there was no statistical significance difference between all the six schools. Alternative hypothesis claimed that there is at least one school that shows statistical significance difference.

Table 6 : One way ANOVA involvement of teachers in finance and managerial

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	237.145	5	47.429	3.040	.012
Within Groups	2808.581	180	15.603		
Total	3045.726	185			

The result of one way ANOVA showed difference the existence of difference (F(1, 185) = 3.04; p=0.012). Gora primary school different by excelling with mean score (M =3.05) Ilala is the least mean values of (M=2.51). This implies that some schools differ involving teachers in management of school with finance involvement better than other. This indicate the absence of clear guide line how and when to involve teachers.

Table 7: Teachers involvement in school facility management

No	Items								Total		
			Gora	Lalistu Gotera	Dirqi Benaso	Ejaji	Ilala	Kersa	N	M	SD
1	Deciding on the expansion of school building	M	3.10	2.39	2.48	2.94	2.48	2.35	186	2.62	1.01
		SD	1.04	0.91	1.09	0.92	0.96	0.95			

2	Deciding on maintenance of school building	M	3.03	2.29	2.45	3.16	2.71	2.68	186	2.72	1.02
		SD	1.08	0.90	0.99	0.93	1.00	1.04			
3	Deciding on construction of new building	M	2.90	2.35	2.58	3.0	2.35	2.77	186	2.66	1.05
		SD	1.04	0.91	1.02	1.12	1.14	0.95			
4	Assigning school building for different purposes										
	M	3.06	2.32	2.58	3.03	2.68	2.81	186			
	2.75										
	1.06										
		SD	1.09	0.90	0.99	1.08	1.16	0.98			
Total average	M	3.022	2.337	2.522	3.032	2.56	2.652	186	2.68	1.03	
		SD	1.062	0.680	1.022	1.012	1.07	0.980			

As can be seen from Table 7, the participation level of teachers' in facility/ building management was found to have been average ($M = 2.68$, $SD = 1.03$, $N = 186$). In the study area, teachers' Participation the assigning school building for administrative, department and teaching purpose is at a modest level ($M = 2.75$, $SD = 1.06$). The finding that says all primary schools in the study are involving teachers' in decision-making practice shows that principals in the study area value teachers very high. That, on the other hand creates the sense of ownership. Teachers are involved in the decision about maintenance of school building ($M = 2.72$, $SD = 1.02$) and the expansion of school building ($M = 2.62$, $SD = 1.01$) both at average level.

The null hypothesis tested was that there is statistically significant difference between the six schools. One way ANOVA with post Hoc was conducted. Computing one way ANOVA was appropriate as the group means to be compared are more than two, (actually, they are six) [12].

Table 8: one way ANOVA school Building.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	197.849	5	39.570	2.99	.013
Within Groups	2374.774	180	13.193		
Total	2572.624	185			
P<0.05;					

The result of one way ANOVA showed the existence of difference ($F(1, 185) = 2.99$; $p=0.013$). Gora primary school and Ejaji did very well in involving teaches in school building management two primary school Ilala and Dirki Benaso behind with report.

Table 9: Over all teachers' involvement.

No	Sample Primary Schools From Elu Gelan District													
	Gora		Lalistu Gotera		Dirqi Benaso		Ejaji		Ilala		Kersa		Total	
Items	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD
1. Average participation planning supervision	2.7	0.7	2.8	0.8	2.8	0.7	2.3	0.9	1.9	1.0	2.7	1.6	2.5	0.9
2. Average participation in curriculum and instruction	2.8	0.8	2.8	0.8	2.6	0.9	2.6	0.8	2.4	1.2	2.6	0.8	2.6	0.9
3. Average participation in school budget and finance	3.0	0.9	2.7	0.9	2.5	0.9	2.9	0.7	2.5	0.9	2.5	0.8	2.7	0.9

4. Average values of teachers involvement in school management	3.0	1.2	2.4	0.9	2.3	0.8	2.5	0.8	1.8	0.7	2.2	1.0	2.4	1.1
Average of Overall Involvement	2.88	0.90	2.60	.085	2.5	0.82	2.5	0.80	2.15	1.95	2.5	1.05	2.52	.11

Table 10: Overall teachers involvement one way ANOVA.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	128.866	5	25.773	2.415	0.038
Within Groups	1920.968	180	10.672		
Total	2049.833	185			

P<0.05;

The result of one way ANOVA showed the existence of difference ($F(2,415) = 0038; p=0.000$). It can be understood that in overall teachers involvement Gora primary school with Mean score of 2.87, $SD = .90$ excel all others; while on the other hand, Ilala primary school performed much lower than the other five schools.

Teachers from Gora associated this to the educational background of the principal, who is trained and qualified with MA in educational leadership. The principal of Ilala is not majoring in leadership.

Table 11: Teachers views regard to meeting Input standards.

No	Items								Total		
			Gora	Lalistu-Gotera	Dirqi Benaso	Ejaji	Ilala	Kersa	N	M	SD
1	Fulfilled and is in line with the set standards for class rooms and other building and facilities	M	2.84	2.74	2.45	2.84	1.74	3.45			
									186	2.68	1.74
2	Fulfilled financial resource to improve the teaching-learning process and execute its priority areas	SD	1.00	0.85	1.23	0.89	0.72	3.51	186	2.58	0.88
		M	2.87	2.48	2.65	2.87	1.97	2.61			
		SD	0.92	0.72	1.14	0.88	0.54	0.66	186	2.55	0.36
3	Sufficient and stably qualified directors teachers and other staff.	M	2.84	2.48	2.48	2.97	1.84	2.68			
4	Created an educational environment which is safe, secure and promotes the well being	SD	0.82	0.89	1.12	0.91	0.68	0.74	186	2.63	.90
		M	3.0	2.45	2.85	2.79	2.03	2.77			
5	Created a well-organized educational development army standard result and grade inspectors' comment.	SD	0.77	0.85	1.02	0.83	0.87	0.71	186	2.99	3.217
		M	4.19	2.45	2.45	2.94	2.35	3.58			
6	The school has shared vision, mission and values.	SD	5.40	0.85	0.99	0.96	0.91	5.32	186	2.63	0.928
		M	3.06	2.58	2.42	2.94	2.35	2.42			
7	The school has prepared participatory school improvement plan	SD	0.99	0.88	0.92	0.89	0.95	0.72	186	2.61	0.948
		M	3.03	2.58	2.26	2.94	2.35	2.52			
		SD	1.04	0.88	0.96	0.92	0.75	0.89		2.66	1.28
	Averages opinion meeting input standards	M	3.12	2.54	2.51	2.89	2.09	2.86			
		SD	1.56	0.845	1.054	0.897	0.774	1.794			

As can be seen from table 11, the average value for having qualified teachers and principals was found to be average ($M=2.66$, SD $P=1.28$). The schools were found to be better off in establishing a well-organized educational army ($M=2.99$, $SD=3.22$). The overall average for meeting input standards for all the six schools was found to be average ($M=2.66$, SD 1.8).

To check whether statistical significance difference exists in meeting input standards between in six sample schools one way ANOVA with post Hoc was computed.

Table 12: Meeting input standards one way ANOVA.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2402.581	5	480.516	3.477	.005
Within Groups	24873.032	180	138.184		
Total	27275.613	185			

$P<0.05$

The result of one way ANOVA showed the existence of difference ($F(1, 185) = 3.477$; $p=0.005$).

It can be understood that meeting input standards was differ.

Table 13: Five year inspection report on input Inspection result for meeting input standard?

No	School	Years					Total school	Average
		2006	2007	2008	2009	2010		
1	Gora	14.5	-	15	14	15	58.5	14.65
2	Lalistu Gotera	12.5	-	13	13.5	14	53	13.25
3	Dirqi Benaso	11.7	-	13	14	13.5	63.2	15.80
4	Ejaji	13.2	-	15.2	15.5	17	60.9	15.22
5	Ilala	13.5	-	14	14	15	56.5	14.13
6	Kersa	13.3	-	14	14.3	15	56.6	14.15
	Total Average	13.11	-	14.03	14.21	14.9	58.11	14.53

As can be seen from table, 13 the five year average inspection report for the six sampled school was 14.53 % out of 25% indicating that the school performance in terms of meeting input standard is average.

Table 14: Teachers and principals responses towards the With regard to Process in schools.

No	Items								Total		
			Gora	Lalis. Gotera	Dirqi Benaso	Ejaji	Ilala	Kersa	N	M	SD
1	Student learning and participation has increased./2/	M	3.16	2.77	2.10	3.42	1.90	2.55			
		SD	1.09	0.95	1.04	0.88	0.79	0.88	186	2.65	1.08
2	Student make progress (have achievement) in their learning./2/	M	3.10	2.84	2.13	3.45	1.74	2.52	186	2.63	1.06
		SD	1.04	1.86	1.11	0.88	0.57	1.85			
3	The student show positive attitude (have behavioral change)./2/	M	3.23	2.61	2.29	3.35	2.00	2.55	186	2.67	1.09
		SD	0.884	0.95	1.18	0.98	0.931	0.81			
4	Teaching is well planned, reflects high expectation of students, and is supported by the use of suitable resources./2/	M	3.13	2.45	2.26	3.26	2.03	3.42	186	2.76	2.47
		SD	0.885	0.96	1.15	1.094	0.795	5.55			
5	Teachers have adequate knowledge of the subject they teach./2/	M	3.16	2.42	2.45	3.19	2.10	2.39	186	2.62	1.01

		SD	0.86	0.88	1.12	1.07	0.90	0.71			
6	The leadership of the school and teachers use appropriate and modern teaching methods that help increase all students' participation	M	2.97	2.35	2.48	3.13	2.03	2.35	186	2.55	1.03
		SD	0.94	0.79	1.18	1.02	1.048	0.75			
7	The school keeps record of data regarding females and student with special needs; it provides special supports./2/	M	3.06	2.32	2.65	3.0	2.06	2.42	186	2.59	0.97
		SD	0.96	0.70	1.14	0.93	0.89	0.76			
8	Teachers, directors and supervisors have undertaken continuous professional development (CPD) program.	M	3.10	2.42	2.35	3.23	2.42	2.45	186	2.66	1.04
		SD	1.07	0.88	1.17	0.88	0.99	0.92			
		M	3.03	2.30	2.40	2.43	2.40	2.34			
	Total Average	SD	0.89	1.12	0.85	0.75	0.97	1.42	186	2.23	1.16

Generally, with regard to process, the average for meeting process standards was found to be almost at average level (M= 2.25; SD = 1.16).

One way ANOVA with post Hoc was conducted. Computing one way ANOVA was appropriate as the group means to be compared are more than two, (actually, they are six)(Gay, Mills, and Airon,2009).Alternatives hypothesis claimed the existence of difference.

Table 15: Meeting Process Standard One way ANOVA.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2626.285	5	525.257	11.235	.000
Within Groups	8415.677	180	46.754		
Total	11041.962	185			

P<0.05;

The result of one way ANOVA showed the existence of difference (F(1, 185) = 11.24; p=0.000). It can be understood that meeting process standards was differ.

This items that assess teaching – learning and administrative processes were considering in evaluating the performance of schools. Teachers rated statements regarding them. As can be seen from table 18, the assessment process was found to be higher than others (M = 2.70, SD = 2.44) indicating that the school improving performance was found to follow it (M = 2.61, SD = 0.99) on teaching process. The leadership of the school and teachers use appropriate and modern teaching methods that help were found to be the lowest (M= 2.55, SD = 1.03). Generally, the with regard to process, the average for meeting process standards was found to be almost at average level (M= 2.57; SD = 1.01).

The null hypothesis tested was that there is statistically significant difference between the six schools. One way ANOVA with post Hoc was conducted. Computing one way ANOVA was appropriate as the group means to be compared are more than two, (actually, they are six) [12].

Table 16: Meeting process standards one way ANOVA.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	676.301	5	135.260	6.375	.000
Within Groups	3819.161	180	21.218		
Total	4495.462	185			

P<0.05

The result of one way ANOVA showed the existence of difference (F(1, 185) = 6.38; p=0.000). It can be understood that meeting process standards was differ.

Table 17: Meeting about Process standard inspection reports from document.

Focuses on Learning and teaching and the school's engagement with parents and the community.

No	Years							Total school		
	School	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010				
1	Gora	20.5	-	22	22.5	22.3	87.3	21.83		
2	Lalistu Gotera	16.5	-	18	20	21	75.5	18.88		
3	Dirqi Benaso	17	-	20	20.5	22	109.5	27.38		
4	Ejaji	19.5	-	21	22	20	82.5	20.63		
5	Ilala	15.3	-	17.5	19	20	72.0	18.00		
6	Kersa	16.5	-	18	18	19	71.5	17.88		
Total Average		17.55	-	19.41	20.33	20.7	83.05	20.77		

Meeting process standard is marked out of 35% present. The four year school performances with respect meeting process standard was found to have been within range between 18.00 for Ilala and 27.38 for Dirki Benaso.

The total average for all the six schools was found to be 20.77 out of 25% showing that it is at average level.

Table 18: Meeting process standards one way ANOVA.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	2626.285	5	525.257	11.235	.000
Within Groups	8415.677	180	46.754		
Total	11041.962	185			

$P < 0.05$;

The result of one way ANOVA showed the existence of difference ($F(1, 185) = 11.24$; $p = 0.000$). Dirki Benaso showed better performance with respect to meeting process standard.

Table 19: Meeting Teachers and principals responses towards the with regard to outcome in schools.

No	Items								Total		
			Gora	Lalis. gotera	Dirqi Beans	Ejaji	Ilala	Kersa	N	M	SD
1	The school has successfully met the national educational access, internal efficiency and educational sector development programs goals.	M	3.32	2.68	2.13	3.10	2.03	2.58	186	2.64	1.14
		SD	1.04	1.27	1.08	1.01	0.98	0.88			
2	The student class room, regional and national examination results have improved in relation to regional and national expectation of the performance of their age groups	M	3.16	2.65	2.16	3.10	2.29	2.48	186	2.64	1.14
		SD	1.19	1.25	1.18	1.01	0.93	0.92			
3	Students demonstrate responsible behavior, ethical values, cultural understanding and protection of their environment.	M	3.32	2.65	2.23	3.16	2.29	2.48	186	2.69	1.16
		SD	1.07	1.27	1.14	1.03	1.03	0.96			
4	There is good communication and interaction among the schools 'teachers, leaders and support staff there is also a sense of accountability and fighting rent-seeking.	M	3.26	2.68	2.19	3.19	2.52		186	2.72	1.19
		SD	1.09	1.27	1.19	1.04	1.23	2.48			
5	The school has secured support due the strong relation it has created with parents, local community and partner organization.	M	3.23	2.68	2.16	3.10	2.26	2.48	186	2.65	1.14
		SD	1.14	1.27	1.15	1.01	0.93	0.96			
	Total averages	M	3.24	2.668	2.17	3.13	2.28	2.50	186	2.66	1.15
		SD	1.10	1.266	1.148	1.02	1.02	0.93			

As can be seen from table 19, there is good communication and interaction among the schools 'teachers, leaders and support staff there is also a sense of accountability and fighting rent-seeking of the study area show more integrity than others measures (M = 2.72; SD = 1.19); followed by student class room, regional and national examination results have improved in relation to regional and national expectation of the performance of their age groups and school has secured support due the moderate relation it has created with parents, local community and partner organization (M = 2.65; SD = 1.14).

Generally, the study areas with regard to outcome in schools level is moderate (M = 2.66; SD = 1.15). Null hypothesis tasted was that there was statically significant difference between six primary schools in outcome [13-15].

Table 20: towards the With regard to outcome.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	676.301	5	135.260	6.375	.000
Within Groups	3819.161	180	21.218		
Total	4495.462	185			

$P < 0.05$;

The result showed that there was statically significance difference (F (1, 185) = 6.38, P = 0.000). It can be understood that with teachers and principals responses towards the With regard to outcome in schools. All school principals were differing.

Table 21: Outcome, Inspection Report on meeting outcomes standards by school years.

Focus: Student outcomes and ethics.

No	Years							Total	
	School	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010			
1	Gora	27	-	30	32	32.5	30.3	30.38	
2	Lalis.Gotera	21	-	23	25	24.8	23.4	23.45	
3	Dirqi Benaso	23.5	-	23	24	25	23.8	23.88	
4	Ejaji	28.5	-	30	33	32	30.8	30.75	
5	Ilala	26	-	28	29	29.4	31	28.10	
6	Kersa	27.5	-	32	32.5	31.23	30.8	30.80	
Total Average	25.58	-	29.33	29.25	29.15	23.7	27.89		

Meeting outcome standard evaluated out of 40%percent. The average inspection report for outcome ranged from 23.45 present for Lalistu Gotera to 30.80, for Gora. The over result for meeting outcome standard for all the six sampled schools were found to be 27.89out of 40% Average.

Table 22: Meeting outcomes standards one way ANOVA.

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	676.301	5	135.260	6.375	.000
Within Groups	3819.161	180	21.218		
Total	4495.462	185			

The result showed that there was statically significance difference (F (1, 185) = 6.38, P = 0.000). It can be understood that with teachers and principals responses towards the With regard to outcome in schools. All school principals were differing.

Table 23: Summary of Inspection Report.

	Schools	2007	2008	2009	Average
Input total out of 25	Input total out of 25				
Process standard out of 35%	Gora	-	22	22.5	22.25
	Lalistu Gotera	-	18	20	19
	Dirki benaso	-	20	20.5	20.25
	Ejaji	-	21	22	21.5
	Ilala	-	17.5	19	18.25
	Kersa	-	18	18	18
Process standard out of 35 Outcome Standard Out of 40	Gora	-	30	32	31

	Lalistu Gotera	-	23	25	24
	Dirki benaso	-	23	24	23.5
	Ejaji	-	30	33	31.5
	Ilala	-	28	29	28.5
	Kersa	-	32	32.5	32.25
Outcome Standard Out of 40 Total inspect result out of 100%	Gora	-	67	68.5	67.75
	Lalistu Gotera	-	54	58.5	56.25
	Dirki benaso	-	56	58.5	57.25
	Ejaji	-	66.2	70.5	68.35
	Ilala	-	59	62	60.5
	Kersa	-	64	64.8	64.4
Total inspect result out of 100% Level of performance	Gora	-	2	2	2
	Lalistu Gotera	-	2	2	2
	Dirki benaso	-	2	2	2
	Ejaji	-	2	2	2
	Ilala	-	2	2	2
	Kersa	-	2	2	2
Level of performance Average		-	2	2	2

The overall average performance of six schools out of 100 ranged between 56.25 to 68.35 with an average of 62.42 this show that the performance level of school what is called level 2 indicate schools are improving, but are not meeting standard.

Relationship between teachers involvement school performance

The third objective of this study was to describe the relation exists between principals' decision-making practice and schools' performance in study area.

Table: 24: Correlation schools.

	Teachers' involvement	School performance
Teachers' involvement	1	
School performance	.72**	1

Accordingly it is significant at ($\gamma=0.072$, $p=0.33$, $N=186$) meaning that there is no significant difference in the level of schools performance and decision making practice. It can be said that there is weak relationship between schools performance and decision making practice.

Conclusions

Based on the analysis of the data and the major findings of the study, the following conclusions were derived in relation to basic questions of the study:

- » Generally, the extent of teachers' participation in decision-making practice in primary schools of Elu Gelan Woreda was minimal. Less attention was given to teachers' contribution to efficiency and effectiveness of school performance through participation in decision making. This, thus, affects the overall activities of school performance in general and decision-making practice in particular.
- » School performance and management in Elu Gelan woreda primary schools us the finding showed us were inadequate. Thus, as the result exhibits us there was inadequate performance which means respondents lowly rate the performances of their school. This was because of decisions were made without participating teachers and gathering necessary information, insufficiency of input fulfilled in the schools, teaching learning process practiced and the outcome of the school was minimal.
- » Concerning the relationship between teachers involvement in school

management and schools' performance, the study revealed that there was a moderate positive correlation between primary school principals' participatory decision-making practice and school performance: [$r(186) = 0.020$, $P < 0.05$]. Consequently, it can be concluded that principals' participatory decision-making had positive impact on the overall performances of school. Moreover, it could be concluded that input and process had moderately positive impact on output the schools understudy so that these have its own impact on the overall performance of schools us the study revealed.

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